

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research

Vol-1, Number 1, March- 2023 | Peer-Reviewed Journal

ISSN 2764-9733 | ijerresearch.org

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8403505

DEMOCRATIC MANAGEMENT AND THE SPECIFICITY OF THE SCHOOL FOR ADOLESCENTS IN COMPLIANCE WITH A SOCIO-EDUCATIONAL MEASURE

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ABSTRACT

In an interdisciplinary approach, we found a possible reading in the analyzed article: “Construction of Meaning in the Narratives of Chronic Patients” and the construction of an analysis based on the expressed content. This construction of speech permeates the entire process of human communication being developed through the relationship of linguistic symbols expressed in speech, that is, in the speech emanated by the subject. Objective: To analyze the content of textual fragments of the article “Construction of meaning in the narratives of chronically ill patients” by José Roque Junges and Tatiane Bagatini under the framework of Moscovici’s social representation. Methodology: Research with a qualitative approach. For treatment of the material, Bardin’s method of content analysis (1977) was chosen, where he analyzes the content and its inferences in a systematic and objective way, described by Minayo (2000), which organizes it in three stages: analysis, exploration of the material and treatment of the results obtained and interpretation under the framework of Moscovici (1979; 2003; 2009). Results and Discussion: In this study, we used the inferences to compose the content analysis categories, associating them by similarity, generating the categories: diagnosis of the disease, therapeutic and drug treatment become (1) Therapeutic, while body and emotional situation become (2) Social Representation. We emphasize that all respondents are in a moment of physical, emotional, and social fragility resulting from the hospitalization process, which limits full autonomy over health decisions and practices. Final Considerations: We found in the analyzes of the study two distinct processes in the discourse confirming our hypothesis about the attitude influenced by everyday experiences, the study presents objectification and anchoring analyzed based on TRS that demonstrate the role of influence of the daily experience and the transformation of the subjective into objective through the hierarchy of responsibility for their reality.

Keywords: Content Analysis, Discourse, Chronic Patient , Social Representation.

INTRODUCTION

This work is the result of my training as a student of the School Management Specialization course, of the National School of Basic Education Managers Program, promoted by the Graduate Program in Education at the Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul.

The in-depth examination of the central theoretical issues studied in that course made this work possible. Thus, in the “Theoretical Reference” section, the authors who contributed to the considerations regarding the themes of the right to education, Democratic Management and the Political-Pedagogical Project are presented.

Quality public education is a right guaranteed by the Federal Constitution of 1988. It is everyone’s right and a duty of the State and the family and must be promoted and encouraged with the collaboration of society as a whole, so that the person has full development and preparation for the exercise of citizenship and qualification for work.

The changes within the school result from democratic management. These changes always indicate a path towards development and training, allowing for improvements in both pedagogical and administrative issues. The democratic manager must present pedagogical spaces that allow students to build learning directed to the exercise of citizenship. In addition to teachers and staff, parents and guardians also participate in these pedagogical spaces. They are spaces for collective participation, rich in learning possibilities for everyone involved in them.

The process of democratic management begins with the elaboration of the school’s political-pedagogical project, which must have the participation of education professionals who work within the scope of the school institution. It is also necessary that the pedagogical project be widely discussed with the entire school community, prioritizing issues such as access, permanence and quality of public education.

In chapter 3, I address action research, defining it as a methodology that allows listening and approximation between all segments of a school community. For these reflections, I relied on

authors such as Maria Amélia Santoro Franco.

Widely used in education, action research presupposes a permanent dialogue between the researched subjects and the researcher, between theory and practice. In this way, a process is built between people in the school community to transform a pre-existing reality, which no longer satisfies, to develop improvements and qualify relationships.

I conclude the work by presenting, in the final considerations, the possibility of applying an intervention project that takes into account the different reality of the school where I work, whose main characteristic lies in the public served: adolescents in compliance with socio-educational measures.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The challenge of this work is to establish a relationship between the right to education and democratic school management, as principles evidenced in practice during the reflection process on the re-elaboration of the Political-Pedagogical Project – PPP of a school with very specific peculiarities in its school community. In the development of the work, it was necessary to deepen theoretical questions that would allow to substantiate the proposed task.

2.1 RIGHT TO EDUCATION

The Federal Constitution of Brazil, of 1988, in its article 205, establishes that education is a right of all and a duty of the State and the family, being promoted and encouraged with the collaboration of society, so that the person has full development and preparation for the exercise of citizenship and qualification for work.

In order for this right to be achieved under the terms guaranteed by the Constitution, the Law of Guidelines and Bases for Education (Law No. State duties in relation to public school education “defining the responsibilities, in collaboration, between the Union, the States, the Federal District and the Municipalities”.

In the process of revision of the Federal Constitution,

which lasted from 1987 to 1988 (Procópio, 2007), the intention to profoundly reorganize the Brazilian political system prevailed. In practice, this did not happen because the attention of the National Congress and institutions turned to the economic priorities that Brazil adhered to at the time, especially after the implementation of the Real Plan and the election of Fernando Henrique Cardoso.

From 1980 onwards, Brazilian democracy gradually solidified in a formal and informal way. The confidence that the population now has in the consolidation of democracy is linked to the experiences acquired in overcoming crises and in improving the socioeconomic conditions of the population. Brazilian education becomes a government strategy within the process of establishing and solidifying democracy in Brazil.

Education is universally regarded as a Human Right; she considers Man in his vocation to always seek something better, to bring about development for himself and his community. Unlike other living beings, human beings always seek to overcome their condition of existence in the world. And he achieves this by making use of his work, transforming nature and living in society. According to Sacavino (2006):

By exercising these capacities, the human being makes history, transforms the world, being present in it in a permanent and active way. And education is a fundamental element for realizing this human vocation, understanding education in its different meanings, in the formal scope of the school system and in the non-formal scope. (SACAVINO, 2006, p.458).

Despite all the national legislation that protects the right to education, the number of Brazilians without access to school and quality education is still significant. Of those who enter school, a large portion cannot remain to complete their schooling, as stated by Sacavino (2006, p.463-464) “Of 100 students who enter elementary school, only 59 manage to finish eighth grade and only 40 reach at the end of high school”.

Of the large portion that drop out of school,

especially in elementary school, many find crime along the way and become part of the group of adolescents who are deprived of their freedom while complying with socio-educational measures.

Given this, we see that the right to education is much broader than the right to school. Educational processes permeate people's entire lives in different dimensions and phases, enabling decision-making that interferes positively or negatively in individuals' lives.

2.2 DEMOCRATIC MANAGEMENT

The function of the democratic manager in education is of fundamental importance to establish the construction of democracy in the country and, as Procópio (2007, p.15) points out, it must be in tune with the “[...] democratization of the demands of the various segments that make up the educational process and the construction of a new shared knowledge .”

The society that demands quality public education from the State is the same that defends a school committed to the community in which it operates, and whose management must be shared by the school community. The defense of democratic school management is based on the premise that all those interested and involved in school life must participate in decisions that affect school life.

In the path of democratic management, vigorous complementary and ordinary legislation has been instituted to build an organizational structure that allows the realization of the objectives and principles of national education. Today, the educational manager can make use of the Statute of the Child and Adolescent – Law nº 8.069, of 1990 – to guarantee access to education and permanence in school, in addition to the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education – Law nº 9.394, of 1996 – and the National Education Plan – Law No. 10,172, of 2001.

According to Medeiros and Luce (2012, p.10), this entire legal framework brings with it measures

of greater participation and social inclusion and serves as a journey “for the democratization of education and the democratization of educational management”.

Democratic management presupposes the idea of participation, of shared work, guided by a collective will and acting on the process of building a competent school committed to society. Like this,

The creation of participatory environments is, therefore, a basic condition of democratic management. One of them is the creation of an overall view of the school and its social responsibility; the establishment of internal and external associations; valuing and maximizing the multiple and diversified aptitudes and competences of the participants; the development of an open, ethical and transparent communication process. This participatory environment gives people the opportunity to control their own work, at the same time that they feel like an organic part of a reality and not just an appendage to it or a mere instrument for achieving its institutional objectives. (LÜCK, 2000, p.27).

A school with quality teaching attracts students instead of repelling them. It is also the function of the director of the school institution, within a democratic management, to present an attractive school to the community. The longer children and adolescents remain at school, the lower the chances of being swept away by crime and its consequent violence.

It is in the process of democratic management that changes occur in schools. The democratic manager presents pedagogical spaces that allow students to build learning aimed at exercising citizenship. The school can be a pedagogical space for collective participation, rich in learning possibilities for the exercise of citizenship.

In the current educational context, the theme “Democratic and Participative School Management” acquires great relevance both for its strategic nature and for its use as a tool for obtaining quality education. Where everyone can contribute to building a school that meets the

demands of the globalized world in its multiple perspectives, that is, in the formation of critical and qualified citizens to meet the demands of the job market. (CABRAL, 2011, p.2).

The perspective of democratic management, according to Cabral (2011, p.2) requires the manager to assume the commitment to re-educate himself, to learn to manage the school together with representatives of all segments of the school community. This will encourage collegiate bodies to become active, taking over, together with the school management, the administrative and pedagogical process of the school institution.

In this way, the entire school community is committed to the performance of the school, both in the pedagogical and administrative spheres. The director no longer acts alone, but promotes his actions in a dialogic perspective, pointing to the construction of democratic instances of deliberation, such as school councils, student unions, thus guaranteeing the exercise of power sharing.

Of the wide range of activities that are incumbent upon the school director, the role of articulator and encourager of the construction and participation of collegiate actions at school stands out. The collegiate bodies make possible and harmonize the discussion process with teachers, employees, students and students’ parents, allowing actions regarding the school’s problems to be taken together, pointing to democratic solutions.

2.3 POLITICAL-PEDAGOGICAL PROJECT

Professor Cury (2005 , p.11), discussing the importance of the role of the democratic manager in the school, emphasizes that the provision of quality teaching presupposes professional quality as well. And, according to him, this process begins with the elaboration of the pedagogical project, which must have the participation of education professionals who work within the school institution.

Therefore, the management of the pedagogical project is a collective task of the teaching staff, led by the manager in charge, and is aimed at

obtaining another constitutional principle of national education, which is the guarantee of the quality standard. [...] Democratic management as a principle of national education, mandatory presence in public school institutions, is the dialogic, participatory way in which the educational community is able to carry out a quality pedagogical project and from which active citizens are born, society participants as committed professionals. (CURY, 2005, p.11).

These statements made by Cury (2005, p.11) provoke profound reflections on public education and its relations with democratic management. The right to education presupposes a duty of the State. Is this duty being fulfilled in order to provide citizens with quality education? Is the performance of education professionals consistent with what the law determines? In practice, are there really guarantees of access, permanence and quality in public schools?

The elaboration, or re-elaboration, of the Political-Pedagogical Project – PPP of a school must be widely discussed with the school community, prioritizing themes such as access, permanence and quality of public education. Access to school must be allowed without differences or discrimination, with respect to the citizen, so that the right to education effectively takes place.

For Luís Armando Gandin , a quality Political-Pedagogical Project moves towards action, but not just any action, because what matters “[...] is not doing many things, but knowing the reason for each one of the things what we do”. For him, the school’s PPP should not be concerned only with the construction of knowledge, but also with the worldview that underpins this knowledge.

Considering that each school is a particular reality, it is possible to state that the school community of each school constitutes a sample of the different realities that make up society. But what about when we have a school that serves only adolescents in situations of deprivation of liberty? What worldview do they bring to school and what underlies their knowledge? In the vast majority of cases, this teenager is part of school dropout statistics. Designing a pedagogical policy

for this student is a huge challenge for the school.

A political-pedagogical project according to Vasconcelos (2009, p.2) is “[...] the result of the interaction between the objectives and priorities established by the community .” And it is this collectivity that establishes, through reflection, the necessary actions to improve their school. This is the starting point for building a PPP: reflecting on the reality of the school community and outlining the goals to be achieved in order to guarantee quality education.

Veiga (2002 , p.11) emphasizes that quality is centered on the challenge of managing the appropriate instruments for its realization. The political-pedagogical project is an instrument that must be experienced at all times by all those involved with the school’s educational process.

The quality school has an obligation to avoid, in every possible way, repetition and evasion. It has to guarantee the qualitative goal of the satisfactory performance of all. Quality for all, therefore, goes beyond the quantitative goal of global access, in the sense that school-age children enter school. It is necessary to guarantee the permanence of those who enter it. (VEIGA, 2002, p.11).

Therefore, once access to the school is guaranteed, it is also the manager’s function to guarantee the permanence of the student in the school space. The causes of evasion must be investigated with the families. The Statute of the Child and Adolescent provides for the measures to be adopted in defense of the guarantee of the right to education and points out the measures to be adopted if the student does not return to school activities, which includes activating both the Tutelary Council and other sectors that act to protect children and adolescents.

Democratic management and the construction of a political-pedagogical project with the participation of the entire school community are requirements for achieving education for all, a right guaranteed by the Federal Constitution.

2.4 RESEARCH-ACTION

Action research is a methodology that brings together theory, implicit in research, and practice, implicit in action. Applied in social sciences and psychology, action research is now widely used in teaching, where it developed in response to the need to implement educational theory in classroom practice.

Such a method is opposed to traditional research, considered objective, non-reactive, which intends to bring knowledge from the outside in, that is, an external expert brings the news to the person in practice. Action research, on the contrary, makes use of participation, of dialogue, seeking to unite research with practical action.

Engel (2000, p.182/183) states that action research constitutes a means of professional development from the inside out, in which teachers, as professionals in educational practice “[...] instead of being only consumers of research done by others, should turn their own classrooms into objects of research”.

The use of this methodology allows research and action to go hand in hand and, with that, the task of re-elaborating the Political-Pedagogical Project will give a new characteristic to school practice: that of participation.

According to Franco (2005, p.485), action research in Brazil has at least three different concepts: collaborative action research, critical action research and strategic action research. The research is collaborative when the search for transformation is requested by the reference group to the research team; is critical when the need for transformation is felt from the researcher’s work with the group, “[...] resulting from a process that values the cognitive construction of experience, sustained by collective critical reflection”, as stated by Franco (2005, p.485); it is strategic when the transformation is previously planned, and, as Franco (2005, p.486) adds, “[...] without the participation of the subjects, and only the researcher will monitor the effects and evaluate the results of its application”.

2.4.1 Action-Research at School with Students in Socio-Educational Measure

The concept of action-research can be adopted, for example, in a school that assists young teenagers in compliance with a socio-educational measure, and it is expected that the researcher perceives, when contacting the group, its needs . Research along these lines would assume a critical character, aiming at the emancipation of the subjects who interact in the process.

Critical action research considers the subject’s voice, perspective, meaning, but not just for recording and subsequent interpretation by the researcher: the subject’s voice will be part of the fabric of the investigation methodology. (FRANCO, 2005, p. 486).

Within a school with the characteristics mentioned above, where students are deprived of liberty, a question arises in relation to the subject’s voice. Who hears them? Who values the students’ verbalization? Professor Carmem Maria Craidy, in an interview with *Educação e Realidade* magazine (2008, p.2), cites examples of boys serving socio-educational measures who become more disciplined and responsible when coordinators, teachers and police officers talk to them.

Knowing that your voice is heard is feeling valued, individualized in the midst of a large group. Even though they temporarily belong to a segregated group, the contact with other adolescents, with coordinators, employees, police and judges allows these individuals, most of whom come from dysfunctional families, to have contact with discipline, responsibility and to be able to rethink their lives based on this interaction. .

Critical action research, in this situation, will also allow adolescents to be heard, to voice their concerns, talk about their needs and what they think the school can do for them and what they themselves can do. for their education , formal or informal. In discussions with other agents about the formative role of the school, adolescents will be able to assume responsibility for their own school development.

Returning to the Brazilian laws that protect children and adolescents, we have, in 1990,

the institution of the Statute of Children and Adolescents - ECA, but, before that, the Constitution of the Republic of 1988, in its article 227, already defined that

It is the duty of the family, society and the State to assure children and adolescents, with absolute priority, the right to life, health, food, education, leisure, professional training, culture, dignity, respect, to freedom and family and community coexistence, in addition to putting you safe from all forms of negligence, discrimination, exploitation, violence, cruelty and oppression. (BRASIL, 1988)

In the case of adolescents involved in infractions, what we know today as a socio-educational measure did not always exist. In the past, adolescent offenders received care without the intention of educating, only of segregation and punishment. Today the measures have an ethical-pedagogical content guaranteed by the legislation.

The Child and Adolescent Statute, in its article 94, items X and XI, determines that the Inpatient Units have the obligation to provide schooling, professional education, cultural, sports and leisure activities to their inmates. And, in the sole paragraph of article 123, it extends activities of a pedagogical nature to provisional hospitalization as well.

The SINASE – National Monitoring System for Socio-Educational Measures, in its chapter Parameters of Pedagogical Management, points out that socio-educational actions should be aimed at the formation of adolescents in the same conception pointed out by Fortunato (2010, p.1) who puts this adolescent “ [...] as an autonomous and solidary citizen who relates well with himself and with the world and that the socio-educational measure has a legal-sanctionary dimension and a substantial ethical-pedagogical dimension .”

In order to comply with the provisions of the Child and Adolescent Statute, on May 28, 2002, the Foundation for Socio-Educational Assistance (FASE/RS) was born, consolidating the process of institutional reordering of the ECA. The Statute determines differentiated treatment for children

and adolescents who are victims of violence and abandonment and adolescents who commit crimes. FASE specializes in providing exclusive assistance to adolescents who have committed infractions with a judicial measure of confinement or semi-liberty.

The service provided at the Foundation is guided by the National System of Socio-Educational Assistance _ SINASE and by the Program for the Execution of Socio-Educational Measures of Internment and Semiliberty - PEMSEIS, whose main axis is the Individual Assistance Plan. The guarantee of individual and collective rights is the basic assumption of technical and administrative intervention, covering pedagogical and therapeutic aspects in the care of adolescents.

With regard to pedagogical aspects, the schooling of adolescents linked to the school under study is developed by the State Department of Education, coordinated by the 1st CRE – Regional Education Coordination, to which teachers report. Adolescents comply with socio-educational internment measures at the same time that they receive formal education from the State.

In this differentiated school, as recommended by the Rio Grande do Sul State Program for the Execution of Socio-Educational Internment and Semiliberty Measures – PEMSEIS/RS, classes have a maximum of ten students . There is a nine-year elementary education offer, Youth and Adult Education in Elementary Education from the 6th to the 9th grade, and Regular Secondary Education. The school has a graded system, with some multigrade classes.

Students are all male, aged between 12 and 21 years old. The number of enrolled students fluctuates daily, bearing in mind that the turnover of these teenagers is part of the specificity of the school. They show a gap in schooling, age and grade in which they are. Most did not attend school before the deprivation of liberty. According to school enrollments, it appears that a significant number is in the 6th year of elementary school.

Having as a parameter the concept of action-research, when carrying out an intervention-

project for the re-elaboration of the Political-Pedagogical Project of the school in question, it will be necessary that the dialogue involve not only the agents of education, but also the agents of the State that control the Unit where the school operates. The dialogic spiral that action research provides may collide with subjects external to the educational process, since the larger structure of a FASE Unit is directly subordinated to the State Department of Justice. Therefore, a discussion around changes in the school should involve agents of education and also of justice.

Considering the peculiarity of this school, it is possible to state that it still exercises the function of guardianship over the inmates, not being characterized as a school with democratic management, in the conceptual range that this term has. It will be necessary to create open spaces that require State actions directed towards a new reality, that the school is multicultural and this diversity is important for the development of the subjects.

In this sense, the work of the school management comes to be understood as a team process, in the perspective pointed out by Lück, (2000) where there is no longer an awareness of administration, but of school management. And this implies a fundamental change in attitude and conceptual orientation. The first step will be to encourage the participation of adolescents in proposing changes that generate improvements in the school. Include them in the situation analysis process, so that they can decide together, also being agents of change.

From this shared work, guided by the desire to seek improvements, a process of collective construction of an educational space that meets the specific needs of this school community will emerge. It is essential to create participatory environments so that students can build a vision that the school is not a punitive and distant entity, but a space where they can exercise their right to a quality education, which directs them towards total development how to be a citizen.

Formal education is a mandatory part of the socio-educational measure applied to adolescents. As the vast majority of them were out of school, for

different reasons, this legal requirement is seen by them not as a right but as a punishment. At first, there is an evident rejection of school activities. Some have time to change their attitude towards a new proposal presented by the school; others, due to the high turnover in the houses, leave as they entered, believing that schoolwork is punitive and not everyone's right.

In view of this, how can a democratic management process be carried out that permeates the elaboration of the Political-Pedagogical Proposal that counts on the participation of all segments in a school whose public is adolescents in compliance with socio-educational measures without the possibility of external activity?

The pedagogical aspect of schools that operate within FASE units must include the generation of opportunities that, after complying with the socio-educational measure, can "... provide a better life perspective for these young people", as stated by Pereira (2013 , p.1).

This is the challenge envisioned from this course. To present a participatory school that can be seen by the student as their right, a possibility to improve their quality of life. New knowledge can generate in these adolescents other perspectives and meanings for school education, allowing social reintegration after fulfilling the socio-educational measure.

3 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

I conclude the work by presenting, as final considerations, the possibility of applying an intervention project that takes into account the different reality of the school where I work, whose main characteristic lies in the public served: adolescents in deprivation of liberty, fulfilling socio-educational measures.

According to research coordinated by Professor Craidy (2008), half of the adolescents who are serving socio-educational measures are out of school, due to abandonment, and come from dysfunctional families. Setting up a school council within the units would bring these families closer to their children's school reality, showing

the importance that family monitoring has on children's development, both in the affective field and in the field of knowledge.

This approximation, however, would need to be accompanied by social workers and health professionals, such as psychologists and therapists. A joint effort that could reach the offender teenager and also the families who, for various reasons, could not closely monitor the development of their children. Any improvement in these relationships would be a gain for those involved in the process.

A research coordinated by Professor Craidy (2008) points out that the coordinators of the houses that receive teenagers in compliance with a socio-educational measure claim that such measures produce some positive effect on a portion of the hospitalized teenagers. They conclude that 18.7% of adolescents are positively influenced by the effect of discipline; 17.3%, due to the impact of responsibility; and 13.3% for the effect caused by the organization.

The logic of time in these places has its own characteristic. These adolescents meet different periods of permanence in the institution. Teachers who work in these schools need to think about different work strategies that address these specific issues. The pedagogical projects have to be of a determined time, in view of the high turnover of students.

A project may cover a maximum period of two months. The evaluations must be done in a procedural way, for each topic, since on the next day one or several students may have been transferred or returned home. The teacher needs to promote reception practices, collective dialogue, differentiated service, seeking to recover values, self-esteem, limits, rights and duties of students.

We are aware that an action-research, to be carried out, needs time and space for each person involved in the process to appropriate the new concepts and build what they want to see changed in their school reality.

Bearing in mind the specificities of the school

under study, and the constant rotation of students, the research could be carried out in the same space, but with different subjects. Although they have the same condition as inmates for offenses committed, it is understood that the needs of each one are different, because man is multiple and diverse by his nature as a human being.

Even in this unique situation, we envision the possibility of preparing a project to discuss with the school community actions aimed at improving the school, thinking about the development of students as a whole.

This perspective that school management can provide dialogue and interaction between education professionals, students and the community arises from participation in the Doctoral Course in Education Sciences at UNIDA University. The theoretical framework made available in the Course enabled us to learn a great deal in the area of school management. This knowledge made it possible to bring about changes in the school routine and in the pedagogical work of the teachers, who felt encouraged to review their pedagogical practices, aiming at better use and learning by the students. We believe that more significant changes can be achieved if it is possible to forward an intervention project that discusses, with the school community and the Department of Justice, practical alternatives aimed at improving the student-school-community relationship in schools that operate within the Units of the Foundation for Socio-Educational Service of the State of Rio Grande do Sul.

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